

Component	Model and part number	Number	Cost per Unit (€)	Total cost (€)	Manufacturer / Supplier	Short link	Material
MAIN PARTS							
Four mass flow controllers, connection cables and power supply unit	MFCs: EL-FLOW Select, power supply unit: E-8501R-00	1	5949.7	5949.7	Bronkhorst	https://bit.ly/3Rf5TH5	Non-specific
Vacuum pump	adixen Pascal 2005SD	1	3171.8	3171.8	Pfeiffer	https://bit.ly/3RiP2mK	Non-specific
Pressure gauge controller	TPG 362	1	2260	2260	Pfeiffer	https://bit.ly/3BGN4qw	Non-specific
Pfeiffer vacuum gauge meter	PCR 280	2	610	1220	Pfeiffer	https://bit.ly/3xS8Ma4	Non-specific
Reactor lid	VPCH42 - Ø2,75" CF Flange, Uncoated UVFS Window	1	253	253	Thorlabs	https://bit.ly/3SfKa33	Non-specific
Reactor main body	-	1	708	708	In-house (LIKAT)	Supplementary Information (fig. S7-S9)	Metal
Saturators	-	2 (pairs)	760	1520	In-house (LIKAT)	Supplementary Information (fig. S1-S6)	Metal
Hg/Xe lamp housing	66901 50-500W	1	3398	3398	Newport	https://bit.ly/3DTwxT2	Non-specific
Hg/Xe lamp power supply unit	OPS-A500	1	5734	5734	Newport	https://bit.ly/3fbXw1l	Non-specific
IR water filter for Hg/Xe lamp	61945	1	971	971	Newport	https://bit.ly/3UGtOIO	Non-specific
Beam turning mirror housing for Hg/Xe lamp	66245	1	511	511	Newport	https://bit.ly/3LNthdR	Non-specific
Hg/Xe light bulb	6291	1	327	327	Newport	https://bit.ly/3BRZg8h	Non-specific

High Power 365nm LED	CUN6F4A	1	2.6	2.6	Neumüller Elektronik GmbH	https://bit.ly/3CcsIH9	Non-specific
Power supply unit LED	TOPS-3602	1	247	247	VOLTCRAFT	https://bit.ly/3fo5G7t	Non-specific
CPU fan and heat sink LED	A200 performance C series	1	3.2	3.2	Xilence	https://bit.ly/3CdyAjz	Non-specific
Spacer Hg/Xe lamp	-	1	26.4	26.4	In-house (LIKAT)	MANUSCRIPT	Metal
Spacer LED	-	1	18.4	18.4	In-house (LIKAT)	MANUSCRIPT	Metal
Cryostat	Pilot ONE ministat 125	1	3750	3750	Huber	https://bit.ly/3frP7rm	Non-specific
Heat tape temperature controller	LTR 4200	1	663	663	Juchheim - Solingen	https://bit.ly/3Sy7hWs	Non-specific
Hot plate and magnetic stirrer	Hei-Tec / PT1000	1	769	769	Heidolph	https://bit.ly/3fo1vZ3	Non-specific
SEALING MATERIALS, VALVES AND CONNECTORS							
Reactor sealing rings	OFC 40 S CF-Dichtung DN 40 CF	1	1.8	1.8	Vakuum-Anlagenbau GmbH		
316L Stainless steel VCR face seal fitting	SS-4-VCR-2-GR	8	6.48	51.84	Swagelok	https://bit.ly/3UCIvXf	Metal
316L Stainless steel VCR face seal fitting, Male NPT connector body 1/4 in. VCR x 1/8 in. MNPT	SS-4-VCR-1-2	8	17.39	139.12	Swagelok	https://bit.ly/3UT9e1Q	Metal
316 Stainless steel Swagelok Tube Fitting, Bulkhead Reducing	SS-400-61-2	2	26.31	52.62	Swagelok	https://bit.ly/3fmTZOI	Metal

Union, 1/4 in. x 1/8 in. Tube OD							
Union Tee, 1/8 in. Stainless steel tube fitting	SS-200-3	7	37.13	259.91	Swagelok	https://bit.ly/3dSc865	Metal
316 Stainless steel nut and ferrule set 1/8in. Tube fitting	SS-200-NFSET	66	6.34	418.44	Swagelok	https://bit.ly/3DUtCcP	Metal
316 Stainless steel nut and ferrule set 1/4in. Tube fitting	SS-400-NFSET	8	5.8	46.4	Swagelok	https://bit.ly/3DY0YYm	Metal
316 Stainless steel nut and ferrule set 1/16in. Tube fitting	SS-100-NFSET	2	11.31	22.62	Swagelok	https://bit.ly/3SzpX8j	Metal
316 Stainless steel Tube Fitting, Zero Volume reducing Union 1/8 x 1/16 in.	SS-200-6-1ZV	1	39.98	39.98	Swagelok	https://bit.ly/3rceqQy	Metal
316 Stainless steel Tube Fitting, Zero Volume reducing Union 1/4 x 1/8 in.		4	1	4	Swagelok		Metal
Stainless steel 2-way ball valve	SS-2P4T	6	99.23	595.38	Swagelok	https://bit.ly/3dNqfd2	Non-specific
Stainless steel 3-way ball valve	SS-41GXS2	2	140.87	281.74	Swagelok	https://bit.ly/3SwwbWq	Non-specific
Stainless steel bellows sealed valve	SS-4BG-V51	4	373.7	1494.8	Swagelok	https://bit.ly/3Cd0v2Y	Non-specific
Stainless steel bellows sealed valve	SS-2H	2	302.91	605.82	Swagelok	https://bit.ly/3LNw7Q3	Non-specific
MISCELLANEOUS PARTS							
Thermal paste	CORSAIR TM30	1	7.99	7.99		https://bit.ly/3Rc90j3	

High-purity pressure regulators and adaptors	VSR-1EC-300-10-00-P-P-00-R-B	2	189.5	379	VIGOUR		Non-specific
Light intensity measuring cell	S405C	1	695.9	695.9	Thorlabs	https://bit.ly/3RgChcs	Non-specific
Light intensity power supply unit	PM100USB	1	422.4	422.4	Thorlabs	https://bit.ly/3fhV361	Non-specific
Laboratory lifting platform	2291	1	229	229	Juchheim Laborgeräte GmbH	https://bit.ly/3xWlXqr	Non-specific
Hose reducers for lamp cooling	ROTILABO E801.1	4	1.68	6.72	Carl-Roth	https://bit.ly/3xVjMnh	Polymer
Tube clamps	ROTILABO N044.1	12	2.7	32.4	Carl-Roth	https://bit.ly/3SzMAcS	Metal
Viton Tube	ROTILABO EX14.1	1	44.8	44.8	Carl-Roth	https://bit.ly/3Cb1gd4	Polymer
SAMPLE HOLDERS							
Sample quartz holder	GT-0172	1	14.2	14.2	NeoLab		Other
SPECIALIZED PARTS							
Hand tube bender	MS-HTB-4	1	281.4	281.4	Swagelok	https://bit.ly/3SfNOKh	Non-specific
Cutter for stainless steel tubes	MS-TC-308	1	75.6	75.6	Swagelok	https://bit.ly/3fqDVeB	Non-specific
Tube deburring tool	MS-TDT-24	1	56.9	56.9	Swagelok	https://bit.ly/3E0XhRw	Metal
TOTAL PRICE (estimation):				37,768			

Notes: In case of parts where there is a minimum ordering amount (e.g., pack of 10) the price per item in this table is calculated by dividing the respective cost. While the photoreactors were built optimized over many years, particular effort was put to include the most recent prices (November 2022). In cases where the originally used parts are discontinued by the manufacturer, a replacement model can be found in the link provided. It should be noted that, these prices are accurate for orders within Germany, and they do not include transportation costs.

For parts manufactured in-house (water-cooled saturators and main body of the photoreactor), the included prices correspond to the sum of their individual constituents as seen in the corresponding figures included in the manuscript and in the supplementary information. In addition, the price for the raw metal used in each of the custom-made parts, correspond to the cost of purchasing 1m of the respective metal.